

ISic0282

I.Sicily inscription 0282

Language

Latin

Type

honorific (?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

Theatre, 1841

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico, inventory 19

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---] C(aius) · Mevius
2. [---p]ont(ifex) · II[vir]
3. [---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491491

EDCS 21900313

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae

Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.6994 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650752>)

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